

Before you start! Download NetLogo 5.3.1:
<https://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/5.3.1/>

SETUP & RUN: Press *SETUP*, click *Run* the simulation will run until you click *Run* again

CONTROL PANEL: To select, click *Set Panel*

CONTROL PANEL

- Panel
- Maps and Settings
- My Own Maps
- Modify Maps
- Stewardship Options
- Display Options
- Advanced Input Options

The screenshot shows the NetLogo interface with the following components:

- File Edit Tools Zoom Tabs Help** menu bar.
- Interface Info Code** tabs.
- EDIT** buttons: Edit, Delete, Add, abc Button.
- normal speed** slider and **view updates** checkbox.
- Settings...** button.
- SETUP & RUN** panel:
 - SETUP** button.
 - Period** dropdown menu (set to 1 day).
 - Run** button.
 - Run for period** button.
 - My Current Map** text field (SYSTEM_Example_Farm.png).
 - My Parameters File** text field (SYSTEM_Example_Farm_Parameters.csv).
- CONTROL PANEL** panel:
 - Panel** dropdown menu (set to Maps and Settings).
 - Set Panel** button.
 - Button 1** (Load Existing Map).
 - Button 2** (Create Map from Scan or load GIS text file).
 - Button 3** (Set Parameter Values).
 - Button 4** (Load Setting).
 - Button 5** (Save Setting).
 - Button 6** (Show or hide Scale Bar).
 - Button 7** (Initial Queens).
- World:** A map showing various land cover types and several bumblebee colonies (represented by icons with numbers like 13, 15, 35).
- RESULTS** panel:
 - GenericPlot 1** dropdown menu (Number of colonies for different species).
 - 45.1** value.
 - 8** value.
 - 143** value.
 - Table:**

Date & Year	Day of Year	# Bees	# Colonies	Colony density
25 April 1	115	378	42	23.2 cols/km2
- Land cover legend:**

Land cover	NetLogo "color"
Scrub	Magenta (125)
Woodland	Brown (35)
Hedgerow	Blue (105)
Grassland	Pink (135)
Improved	Violet (115)
Field beans	Red (15)
Oilseed rape	Yellow (45)
Maize	Green (55)
No resources	Grey (5)

The **'World'**: this is where your map and your bumblebee colonies appear.

Twiston-Davies, Becher & Osborne. [DATE]. BEE-STEWARD: a research and decision support software for effective land management to promote bumblebee populations. [JOURNAL,(,)-].

RESULTS: Graphical results of your simulation. **TIP:** To change, click on the dropdown arrow and select a new plot before you run a new simulation

This Output box will give you updates on your simulation. **TIP:** Results from Task 3 after clicking **Show Stewardship Areas** will appear here

Task 1: Run for 1 year.
SETUP | **Period** | select 1 year from dropdown list | **Run** for period

Task 2: Change Crops.
CONTROL PANEL *Modify Maps* | *Set Panel* | *Replace Colours* | **OK** | click on red swatch | **Yes** | click on a green field | *Update current Map* | rename your map | **No** | **OK**

Task 3: Apply Stewardship.
CONTROL PANEL *Stewardship Options* | *Set Panel* | *Select Stewardship Option (Legume)* | *Select Field* | click on a crop field in your map | *Apply Stewardship* | rename you map | **OK**

Task 4: Load in a picture map.
CONTROL PANEL *Maps and Settings* | *Set Panel* | *Create Map from Scan or load GIS text file* | **No** | **Yes** | select your map as an image file or e.g. *_SYSTEM_Example_Farm.png* | select *Distance any two points* from dropdown | **OK** | **OK** | click on start and then the end of a field edge you know the distance of | **OK** | type the distance e.g. 190 | **OK** | rename you map | **OK**